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Physical Activity Engagement and Disaster Preparedness among College Students

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Abstract

College students participating in regular physical activity may be better equipped to respond to disasters due to increased physical fitness and mental resilience. This study assessed the level of physical activity engagement and disaster preparedness among college students, examined the relationship between physical activity engagement and disaster preparedness, and informed interventions to promote healthier lifestyles and effective disaster response on campuses. The descriptive-correlational survey method was employed to investigate demographic profiles, levels of physical activity engagement, and disaster preparedness among college students. Furthermore, the findings showed a significant relationship between physical activity engagement and disaster preparedness among college students. Thus, the researchers recommended future researchers as a reference point, expanding upon its findings through additional studies or exploring different aspects of physical activity engagement and disaster preparedness among college students.

Keywords: *physical activity engagement, disaster preparedness, college students*

Introduction

Physical activity is any movement that requires energy expenditure and can be performed during leisure time, transportation, or work activities (Hallmann & Giel, 2018). Both moderate and intense physical activity have proven health benefits, including preventing chronic illnesses like diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and certain cancers (Wu et al., 2019). Engaging in regular physical activity during childhood is associated with improved cardiorespiratory fitness and a reduced risk of depression and other mental health issues (Chaput et al., 2020). Despite the well-documented benefits of physical activity, a significant portion of the population remains insufficiently active, posing a severe public health concern World Health Organization (2020). In 2016, approximately 28% of adults aged 18 and above needed to meet the recommended worldwide standard of 150 minutes of moderate-intensity physical activity or 75 minutes of vigorous-intensity physical activity per week World Health Organization (2018). This lack of physical activity contributes to an increase in the prevalence of chronic diseases and adverse health outcomes.

On the other hand, disaster preparedness is crucial for safeguarding communities and mitigating the impact of emergencies and crises. Physical activity can be pivotal in disaster preparedness, as physically active individuals are generally better equipped to handle emergencies (Zhang & Chen, 2019). Encouraging individuals to engage in regular physical activity is vital for both their health and the overall disaster preparedness of communities. The effectiveness of disaster-related programs as interventions for raising disaster awareness and preparedness include awareness campaigns, simulations, training, and exercises (Tkachuck, 2018).

According to the research of Hendrickson et al., 2018, physically active students responded significantly quicker to emergencies, indicating stronger individuals can evacuate more efficiently. However, a lack of physical activity may cause longer evacuation durations, increasing injury and hazard risk for students during disasters. According to Rasteiro et al. (2023) based on the findings, physically active yet untrained students may perform better during disaster evacuation. They have concluded that physical exercises during the emergency response phase would also benefit the general population. Students who are not physically fit may not be able to fully participate in community-wide initiatives such as search and rescue or resource distribution. Another study has shown that lower levels of physical fitness are associated with an increased risk of injury and death during disasters (Hendrickson et al., 2018).

A disaster preparedness intervention can include efforts to improve the capacity of people, communities, governments, and non-governmental organizations (Bay et al., 2021). A school preparedness program is also called integrating a disaster preparedness program in the school community. This program is urgently required in schools situated in disaster-prone locations (Sajow et al., 2019). That is why a school should have a disaster management plan (for the time before, during, and after a disaster), logistical availability, safety and comfort for students, infrastructure and emergency systems supported by knowledge and preparedness, standard operating procedures, and early warning systems (Sujarwo et al., 2018).

A variety of factors link physical activity and disaster preparation among college students. Regular physical activity is essential to disaster preparedness (Smith et al., 2020). Physical fitness improves individuals' endurance and strength, allowing them to withstand physical demands during emergencies, and physical activity promotion frequently emphasizes health and safety awareness, an essential component of disaster preparedness (Jones et al., 2018). In addition, physical activity may instill a sense of responsibility for one's well-being and build a proactive mentality. Not only that, but physical activity participants are also more likely to be aware of the necessity of safety protocols, potential risks, and emergency procedures, which can be transferrable abilities in catastrophe scenarios (Brown et al., 2019). Furthermore, regular physical activity necessitates discipline, time management, and goal-setting, which are essential for disaster preparedness planning (Garcia et al., 2021). The study on physical activity engagement and disaster preparedness among college students reveals several research gaps. There is a limited exploration of the direct impact of physical activity on students'

readiness for disasters, including whether regular exercise influences psychological resilience or practical preparedness behaviors. Additionally, the role of different types of physical activities and their intensity levels in fostering disaster preparedness remains underexplored

This study is anchored to the Conservation of Resource Theory (COR), proposed by Stevan E. Hobfoll. This theory provides a valuable framework for understanding the relationships between physical activity engagement, disaster preparedness, and college students' resource environments (Hobfoll, 1989). According to this idea, people try to acquire and keep resources to deal with demands and challenges. Regular physical activity is a significant resource for improving physical fitness, resilience, and coping methods (Lindell, 2011). Furthermore, according to the theory, people who engage in more physical exercise regard themselves as better suited to deal with disasters, which leads to increased preparedness behaviors (Paton, 2013).

In terms of significance, this study has the potential to yield significant benefits for both individuals and communities. The primary beneficiaries of this study are college students themselves. By investigating the relationship between physical activity engagement and disaster preparedness, the study can provide valuable insights and recommendations for students to enhance their safety and well-being. It can empower them to adopt healthier lifestyles through increased physical activity while equipping them with the knowledge and skills to effectively respond to emergencies. Academic institutions and universities can leverage the findings of this study to gain a deeper understanding of the preparedness levels of their student population. With this knowledge, institutions can develop targeted programs and interventions to improve disaster preparedness on campus (Jones et al., 2018). By integrating disaster preparedness education, physical activity promotion, and safety measures into their policies and practices, universities can create a safer environment for their students during crises (Brown, 2020). Understanding the relationship between physical activity engagement and disaster preparedness enables these stakeholders to develop tailored strategies to mitigate risks and respond effectively to emergencies (Williams et al., 2021).

Moreover, public health and disaster management practitioners can benefit from this research by gaining valuable insights into the role of physical activity engagement in disaster preparedness among college students. Understanding how physical activity affects disaster preparedness can lead to the development of more effective disaster management strategies and public health interventions. By incorporating physical activity promotion into disaster preparedness programs, practitioners can enhance community resilience and reduce the impact of disasters on college campuses (Brown & Lee, 2020). Lastly, future researchers in the fields of public health, disaster management, physical activity, and related disciplines can build upon the findings of this study. It can serve as a foundation for further investigations and contribute to the existing body of knowledge in these areas. Researchers can use the study as a reference point, validating or expanding upon its findings through additional studies or exploring different aspects of physical activity engagement and disaster preparedness among college students.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to determine physical activity engagement and disaster preparedness among UM Digos College students. Specifically, this study aimed to address the following inquiries:

1. To determine the demographic profile among college students in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender; and
 - 1.3. department.
2. To determine the level of physical activity engagement among college students in terms of;
 - 2.1. types;
 - 2.2. frequency;
 - 2.3. intensity;
 - 2.4. duration; and
 - 2.5. total length.
3. To determine the level of disaster preparedness among college students in terms of;
 - 3.1. community-related disaster preparedness;
 - 3.2. disaster information for the family; and
 - 3.3. disaster supply kit/ vehicle at home.
4. To determine if there is a significant relationship between physical activity engagement and disaster preparedness among college students.

Literature Review

Physical Activity

Physical activity encompasses any movement that necessitates energy utilization and can be undertaken during leisure, transit, or work-related tasks (Hallmann & Giel, 2018; World Health Organization, 2010). Both moderate and vigorous physical activity have demonstrated significant health advantages, such as preventing chronic conditions like diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and specific

types of cancer (Lee et al., 2012; Wu et al., 2019). Consistently participating in physical activity during childhood is linked to enhanced cardiorespiratory fitness and a decreased likelihood of experiencing depression and other mental health disorders (Chaput et al., 2020).

Physical fitness can enhance an individual's ability to endure and strengthen their physical capabilities, enabling them to survive the physical challenges that may arise during catastrophes. Promoting physical activity often highlights the importance of being mindful of health and safety, a crucial aspect of being prepared for disasters (Jones et al., 2018). Furthermore, engaging in physical activity can cultivate a sense of accountability toward one's health and foster a proactive mindset. In addition, individuals who engage in physical activity are more likely to possess knowledge regarding safety measures, potential dangers, and emergency procedures. These skills can be applied in situations involving catastrophic events. Collaboration and coordination, sometimes facilitated by engagement in physical activities, are essential for successful disaster response and preparedness efforts (Brown et al., 2019). Individuals must engage, communicate, and synchronize their efforts in team sports or group fitness activities. These skills are advantageous during emergencies as they facilitate efficient collaboration and cooperation, leading to coordinated reactions and mutual assistance among college students.

Disaster Preparedness

Ensuring communities are well-prepared for disasters is essential to protect them and minimize the effects of catastrophes and crises. Engaging in physical exercise is crucial for disaster preparedness, as those who are physically active are typically more capable of effectively managing situations (Zhang & Chen, 2019). Disaster preparedness intervention encompasses initiatives to enhance the capabilities of individuals, communities, governmental bodies, and non-governmental organizations (Bay et al., 2021). A school preparedness program, also known as integrating a disaster preparedness program in the school community, refers to incorporating measures and strategies to ensure readiness for potential disasters within the school environment. It is imperative to implement this program in schools located in areas prone to disasters (Sajow et al., 2019). School disaster preparation refers to the capacity of the community or specific school elements to effectively handle and control calamities (Sujarwo et al., 2018). The study by Kusumastuti et al. (2021) demonstrates using flexible systems to minimize and overcome hazardous consequences. When a school has a comprehensive disaster management plan encompassing the pre-, during, and post-disaster phases, along with logistical readiness, student safety and well-being, robust infrastructure, and emergency systems backed by knowledge and preparedness, standard operating procedures, and early warning systems, these requirements are fulfilled (Sujarwo et al., 2018).

Physical Activity and Disaster Preparedness

Students who engage in regular physical activity demonstrated considerably faster response times to emergencies, suggesting that persons with greater physical strength can evacuate more efficiently. Nonetheless, a deficiency in physical activity might lead to extended evacuation durations, heightening the likelihood of harm and danger for students in the event of disasters (Hendrickson et al., 2018). According to the study conducted by Rasteiro et al. in 2023, the research findings suggest that physically fit but untrained students may exhibit superior performance when evacuating after a disaster. It has been determined that engaging in physical workouts during the emergency response period would also benefit the general public. Physically unfit students may not fully engage in community-wide endeavors such as search and rescue or resource distribution. A recent study conducted by Hendrickson et al. (2018) has demonstrated a correlation between reduced levels of physical fitness and a higher likelihood of injury and mortality in the event of disasters.

Regular physical activity requires discipline, effective time management skills, and the ability to create goals. These qualities are crucial to plan and prepare for potential disasters (Garcia et al., 2021). Students adept at time management and adhering to fitness regimens are more inclined to dedicate time to gaining knowledge, constructing emergency kits, and practicing evacuation drills. Engaging in physical activity can help develop self-discipline, fostering proactive behaviors for preparing for disasters. Promoting regular physical activity is crucial for individuals' well-being and the overall resilience of communities in the face of disasters. Disaster-related activities, such as awareness campaigns, simulations, training, and exercises, are effective treatments for increasing disaster awareness and preparedness (Tkachuck, 2018).

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive-correlational survey method to determine the relationship between variables (McBurney & White, 2009). This method involved gathering data through a survey to describe the characteristics and behaviors of the population and then analyzing the data to identify any correlations or associations between different variables (Creswell, 2016). The survey used in this study included questions about the students' physical activity engagement levels, such as the types of physical activity they engaged in, the frequency and duration of their physical activity, and their overall level of physical fitness. The survey also included questions about their disaster preparedness, such as community-related disaster preparedness, disaster information for the family, and disaster supply kit/vehicle at home. Using the descriptive-correlational survey method provided valuable information about the relationship between college students' physical activity and their preparedness for disasters. It also served as a direction for future studies and programs to help college students be better prepared in times of disaster.

Respondents

In this study, the respondents were the selected first-year to fourth-year college students enrolled in S.Y. 2022-2023. The participants employed in this study were a total of 300 respondents. Additionally, when selecting respondents, the researchers determined the sample by utilizing stratified random sampling. In the context of physical activity engagement and disaster preparedness among colleges, strategically random sampling involved selecting a representative sample of students from different areas of study, levels of physical activity engagement, and levels of prior experience with disaster preparedness. Gender-wise, the majority of students were female (59.3%), followed by men (39%), while a tiny minority (1.7%) identified as LGBTQ+. The age breakdown showed that the most significant percentage of students were between 18 and 20 (51.0%), closely followed by those between the ages of 21 and 23 (46.3%). The 24-to-28-year-old age group accounted for fewer responses (2.7%).

Instrument

The study used two adapted questionnaires developed by Ono et al. (2007) to assess students' level of physical activity engagement. The questionnaires covered type, frequency, intensity, duration, and overall length of physical activity during leisure time. The first question aimed to identify adults' various physical activities during their leisure time, categorizing them into five types: aerobic exercise sports, flexibility exercises, muscular exercises, arts & cultural activities, and sedentary activities. The second question asked about the frequency of physical activity in respondents' free time, the intensity of leisure participation, and the duration of physical activity participation. The overall length of participation was measured using the questionnaires.

On the other hand, to determine the level of disaster preparedness among students, the researchers utilized the household survey instrument on disaster preparedness by Heagele et al. (2020). The questionnaire focused on community disaster preparedness and included a 17-item questionnaire measuring three aspects: community-related disaster preparedness (three items), disaster information for the family (six items), and disaster supply kit/vehicle at home (eight items). Each item used a 5-point Likert-type response format, with values ranging from 1 to 5.

Procedure

The research procedure included multiple steps for data collection. Initially, the researchers acquired an official approval letter from the school administrators. Additionally, the researchers created a series of survey questionnaires for validation. Additionally, the research adviser and experts thoroughly reviewed and validated the survey questionnaires. Finally, the researchers gathered data by conducting a questionnaire that asked participants about their age, gender, and the departments to which they belonged. Once the research adviser and experts approved the survey questionnaires, the researchers gathered data through a detailed questionnaire that included information about participants' ages, genders, and departments. Once the respondents completed the questionnaire, it was thoroughly reviewed, compiled, interpreted, and analyzed following the study's objectives.

To thoroughly analyze the data, the researchers employed a formula that focused on the frequency and distribution of various factors. This allowed them to determine the overall percentage of respondents based on age, gender, and department. An assessment was conducted to measure the level of physical activity engagement and disaster preparedness among college students using relevant indicators.

Data Analysis

The study firmly adhered to the ethical protocols and guidelines. Therefore, the researcher diligently requested and secured necessary permissions from key school officials to proceed with the research. The appropriateness of selected recruitment parties was ensured, and a detailed analysis of the level of risk was undertaken, as well as steps to mitigate these risks, which included physical, psychological, and socioeconomic factors. Specifically, procedures were taken to handle the data, including but not limited to Voluntary Participation, Privacy and Confidentiality, Informed Consent Process, Risks, Benefits, Plagiarism, Fabrication, Falsification, Conflict of Interest, Deceit, Permission from the Organization/Location, and Authorship.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents, which was analyzed based on the age, gender, and department of the 300 respondents who were college students.

Gender-wise, the majority of students were female (59.3%), followed by men (39%), while a tiny minority (1.7%) identified as LGBTQ+. The age breakdown showed that the most significant percentage of students were between 18 and 20 (51.0%), closely followed by those between the ages of 21 and 23 (46.3%). The 24-to-28-year-old age group accounted for fewer responses (2.7%). The Department of Criminal Justice Education (DCJE), which accounted for 30.7% of the respondents, was where most students were enrolled in terms of departmental distribution. The Department of Teacher Education (DTE) (27.7%) and the Department of Business Administration (DBA) (23%) were also noteworthy. In comparison, the percentages for the Department of Arts and Science (DAS) (9%), the Department of Technical Programs (DTP) (6.7%), and the Department of Accounting Education (DAE) (3%) were smaller.

Table 1. Demographic profile of respondents

Demographic		f	%
Gender	FEMALE	178	59.3
	LGBTQ+	5	1.7
	MALE	117	39
Age	18-20	153	51.0
	21-23	139	46.3
	24-28	8	2.7
Department	DAE	9	3
	DAS	27	9
	DBA	69	23
	DCJE	92	30.7
	DTE	83	27.7
	DTP	20	6.7
Total		300	100%

Level of Physical Activity Engagement Among College Students

Table 2 shows the level of physical activity engagement among college students as analyzed according to types, frequency, intensity, duration, and total length focused on the 300 students enrolled in UM Digos College. Overall, the mean of 3.06 (SD = 0.85) suggests a "moderate" level of physical activity, indicating frequent engagement in exercise. Moderate physical activity strengthens our bodies by increasing endurance, flexibility, and overall physical resilience. In a disaster, such as an earthquake or a flood, physical strength is essential for overcoming obstacles, assisting rescue efforts, and reducing the danger of injuries. Furthermore, it gives students the physical strength to handle problems during a disaster. Notably, this is supported by the American Heart Association, which recommends at least 150 minutes of moderate-intensity exercise per week for adults.

Table 2. Level of physical activity engagement among college students

	\bar{x}	SD
Types	3.77	0.97
Frequency	3.00	1.18
Intensity	3.33	0.96
Duration	2.51	1.17
Total Length	2.71	1.26
PA Overall	3.06	0.85

The study of Rodriguez et al., 2019 supports the result of this study, underscoring the positive impact of regular, moderate physical activity on health and well-being, preventing chronic diseases, and promoting psychosocial well-being. Additionally, adolescence is one of the earlier stages of adult life in which physical exercise is practiced (Portela et al., 2021). However, concerns arise from studies like Oliveira et al. (2018), indicating a significant decline in physical activity levels as students transition from secondary to higher education, leading to increased morbidity and mortality.

Moreover, Rodriguez et al. (2019) emphasize the importance of understanding behavioral patterns for targeted intervention programs in promoting healthy habits among college students. Guthold et al. (2018) noted that the evolving effects of inactivity have heightened the significance of studying physical activity levels in teenagers and university students.

Types. The first indicator in Table 2, in terms of types acquired a mean of 3.77 (SD = 0.97), signifies a "high" level of physical activity engagement among college students. This suggests that students frequently participate in various activities, such as cardiovascular and flexibility exercises. Regular physical activity builds our bodies in a way that increases flexibility, endurance, and adaptability. In an emergency, such as an earthquake or a significant storm, physical strength elevates rescue efforts and lowers the chance of injury. Maintaining fitness through cardio exercises, strength training, and flexibility routines enhances physical preparedness. This finding aligns with Orcajada et al., 2013 research, emphasizing the positive impact of physical exercise on teenagers' physical fitness and body composition. According to the World Health Organization (2018), regular physical activities, such as strength training, aerobics, running, swimming, and yoga, are crucial for addressing different muscle groups and increasing overall fitness.

Frequency. On the other hand, the second indicator, as reflected in Table 2, had a mean of 3.00 (SD = 1.18), suggesting a "moderate" level of physical activity engagement, denoting that physical activity engagement is sometimes observed among college students. Regularly engaging in moderate physical activity is essential for maintaining good health and overall fitness. It strengthens the body, boosts the immune system, and improves mental well-being. Moreover, it equips students with the physical resilience necessary to face challenges during a disaster. Students are observed participating in diverse activities 4 to 5 days a week and are advised to engage in muscle-strengthening activities two or more days a week (World Health Organization, 2010). The U.K. Department of Health and Social Care (Department of Health and Social Care, 2019) has accepted the same guidelines. Research reinforces the importance of moderate aerobic exercises, correlating them with cardiorespiratory health. However, significant risk reductions are noted when

physical activity levels reach 150 minutes per week or higher (Zahrt & Crum, 2020).

Intensity. Moving to the third indicator, with a mean of 3.33 ($SD = 0.96$), it also indicates a "moderate" level of physical activity engagement, suggesting that it is sometimes observed among college students. Engaging in physical activities that revolve around disaster preparedness empowers students by instilling a sense of self-confidence and resilience. Students learn about potential hazards and develop the skills to respond effectively; they become more self-assured in handling challenging situations. While students engage in moderate physical activity, the (World Health Organization, 2018) guidelines suggest 150-300 minutes of moderate- or vigorous-intensity physical exercise per week. Notably, only 27.1% of American high school students meet the recommended levels, indicating a potential area for improvement in promoting physical activity among college students (Song & Kim, 2021). In like manner, according to Thompson (2022), the suggestion of performing vigorous exercise three to four days a week further emphasizes the need for targeted intervention programs.

Duration. Table 2 displays the duration of physical activity engagement among college students, with a mean of 3.77 ($SD=0.97$), which implies a "moderate" level of physical activity engagement in terms of duration; it indicates that the college students occasionally engage in physical exercise. Regular physical activity boosts overall health and resilience, equipping students to face the challenges of disasters. Engaging in moderate or vigorous physical activities, such as brisk walking, jogging, or aerobics, strengthens the cardiovascular system, builds endurance, and enhances immunity. The recommended duration for adults by the World Health Organization is highlighted, emphasizing the importance of balancing physical exertion with adequate recovery. However, it is crucial to note the uncertainties in the relationship between physical activity and cognitive function. According to the study Lu (2022), participants were encouraged to repeat movements during a 20-second workout, followed by a 10-second rest period. Adults should engage in 150–300 minutes of moderate physical activity, 75–150 minutes of vigorous physical activity each week, or an equivalent combination of both activities (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2018).

Total Length. The last indicator in Table 2 obtained a mean of 2.71 ($SD= 1.26$), suggesting a "low," implying that physical activity engagement is rarely observed among college students. Despite the clear advantages of physical activity in disaster preparedness, some students may need help engaging in regular physical activity. These challenges could include lack of motivation, limited access to resources or facilities, time constraints, or simply a preference for sedentary activities. The total length of engagement, occurring 1-2 times monthly, indicates a rare involvement in physical activity. Brown's (2019) findings align with this, emphasizing variations in monthly physical activity levels among students. As Van et al. (2021) highlighted, seasonal differences and external factors, such as test seasons and school activities, as noted by (Perez & Smith, 2020), further contribute to the varying engagement levels. Additionally, Martinez Garcia (2018) stresses the role of parental involvement and peer pressure in encouraging physical activity. Endozo (2019) stresses that the respondents' lack of time owing to hectic class schedules was the most important reason for not engaging in physical exercise.

Level of Disaster Preparedness Among College Students

Table 3 presents the level of disaster preparedness among college students. It produced a mean score of 3.85 ($SD= 0.67$), indicating a high readiness level. This implies that, on average, the students surveyed show a greater preparedness for future disasters, pointing to a thorough approach to preparation that considers various factors. According to (Turan et al., 2017), education is essential for giving people knowledge and helping them apply it to their daily lives. Benaben, Sakurai, and Tapia (2019) noted that increased awareness of disasters is correlated with the amount of information gathered about them. Thus, regardless of programs, emphasizing the value of disaster preparedness will likewise increase students' readiness.

Table 3. *Level of Disaster Preparedness Among College Students in terms of:*

	\bar{x}	SD
Over-all Community Related Disaster Preparedness	3.62	0.88
Overall Disaster Information for the Family	3.89	0.75
Overall Disaster Supple Kit/ Vehicle at Home	4.07	0.75
Disaster Over-all	3.85	0.67

Community-related disaster preparedness. Table 3 presents the level of disaster preparedness in terms of community-related disaster preparedness, revealing a mean score of 3.62 ($SD= 0.88$). This suggests a high degree of preparedness. College students often showcase a proactive approach to potential disasters by exhibiting a high level of readiness in community-related disaster preparedness. The importance of the community in disaster recovery has grown in the last few years. In particular, the role of local knowledge, action, participation, and control in shaping the nature of disaster response has been emphasized (Benaben et al., 2019). People learn more about disaster preparedness the more involved they are in society.

Disaster Information for the Family. Under this, disaster information for the family's level produced a mean score of 3.89 ($SD = 0.75$). This suggests that the participants' relatives share a high mean value of information. Families are viewed as the fundamental unit in disaster behavior (Drabek et al., 1986). Families need to know about disasters because it makes them more prepared, less vulnerable, and able to respond to emergencies quickly. Communication is essential to foster resilience and guarantee safety in times of emergency. This argument is supported by the fact that family disaster behaviors remain and adapt to natural and man-made disturbances. Families

are vital reproductive and social structures (Clason, 1983).

Disaster Supply Kit/ Vehicle at Home. Furthermore, regarding disaster supply kits and vehicles at home, a mean score of 4.07 (SD=0.75) suggests a very high degree of preparedness. On average, college students consistently maintain a high level of readiness by having disaster supply kits or vehicles at home, indicating a solid commitment to preparedness measures. Disaster supply kits and emergency vehicles are essential for proactive preparedness against natural and man-made calamities. An entirely stocked bag guarantees rapid access to food, water, first aid supplies, and communication devices, facilitating early crisis intervention (FEMA, 2020). However, having emergency vehicles, including evacuation-ready cars, guarantees that families may evacuate impacted locations promptly and safely, minimizing the probability of harm during disasters (NHTSA, 2019).

Physical Activity Engagement and Disaster Preparedness Among College Students

The results in Table 4 show the correlational matrix between physical activity engagement and disaster preparedness among college students. The results show a strong and statistically significant association between physical activity engagement and disaster preparedness among college students. Starting with the types of physical activity, the positive correlation coefficient of 0.338 ($p < 0.01$) suggests that students' diverse physical activities are related to a higher level of preparation for various disasters. This shows that a diverse range of physical activities may help to develop a more adaptable collection of skills and capacities that will be useful in an emergency. Moving on to the frequency dimension, the correlation value of 0.284 ($p < 0.01$) indicates that more frequent physical activity is associated with higher degrees of disaster preparedness. This means regular physical activity may promote discipline and habits, resulting in a more proactive approach to disaster preparedness among college students.

Table 4. Correlation matrix between physical activity engagement and disaster preparedness

	Community-Related Disaster Preparedness	Disaster Information for Family	Disaster Supply Kit	Disaster Overall
Types	.338**	.276**	.245**	.337**
Frequency	.284**	.246**	.238**	.337**
Intensity	.298**	.221**	.216**	.286**
Duration	.325**	.227**	.149**	.280**
Total Length	.321**	.231**	.204**	.300**
Physical Overall	.394**	.304**	.278**	.383**

** $p < .01$

Regarding intensity, the positive correlation value of 0.298 ($p < 0.01$) indicates that the intensity of physical exercise is positively related to disaster readiness. This could imply that people who participate in more strenuous physical activities have greater resilience and endurance, which are helpful in the face of complex and unexpected events. However, the duration of physical activity also shows a strong positive correlation, with a value of 0.325 ($p < 0.01$). This research implies that more extended periods of physical activity are linked to improved disaster preparedness. Extended physical activity periods help develop perseverance and stamina, essential in emergencies.

Furthermore, total length includes cumulative time spent on physical activity and has a positive correlation coefficient of 0.321 ($p < 0.01$). This suggests that a more significant total investment in physical exercise is associated with improved disaster preparedness. This emphasizes the significance of persistent and consistent participation in physical activities in establishing a solid foundation for disaster readiness. The Physical Overall category, which has a significant correlation value of 0.394 ($p < 0.01$), captures the overall association between physical fitness and disaster readiness. Therefore, the findings show a significant relationship between physical activity engagement and disaster preparedness among college students. This suggests that being physically active in various ways, doing so regularly, including challenging exercises, and maintaining this over time are closely related to being disaster-prepared.

In a study by Markland and Ingledew (2012), college students who are more intrinsically motivated to engage in physical activity for reasons like enjoyment or fitness are likelier to exhibit preparedness behaviors like having supplies and an emergency plan. On the other hand, additional research by Paton (2013) stated that those who engage in more physical activity believe they are better prepared to handle emergencies. Encouraging students to engage in fun and independent physical activities may increase self-assurance and become more prepared for disasters.

According to Senka Bajić et al. (2023), physical fitness might affect first emergency response times, particularly in students. Furthermore, the Katayama et al. (2021) study highlights how combining weekly exercise with disaster prevention training improves participants' self-efficacy, which may improve health promotion and disaster prevention behavior. These studies add to a more complex understanding of how physical activity engagement and disaster preparedness interact.

Conclusions

Based on the results and findings obtained in the conduct of this research study, the following conclusions were drawn: The level of physical activity engagement, when analyzed according to types, frequency, intensity, duration, and total length, indicated that college students' engagement in physical activity was "moderate," signifying their regular participation in physical activity. Students likely incorporated regular physical activity into their routines without resorting to severe sedentary behavior or intense training, contributing

to a holistic and long-term approach to overall health. Additionally, college students were evaluated as having had a high level of preparedness for disasters; this suggested that they had taken proactive steps to provide themselves with the information, tools, and plans needed to respond effectively to crises. Their increased preparedness suggested a strong feeling of resilience and responsibility, fostering a safe and well-prepared community within the collegiate setting. Furthermore, the data revealed a significant relationship between physical activity engagement and disaster preparedness among college students. This suggested that being physically active in various ways, doing so regularly, including challenging exercises, and maintaining this over time were closely related to being disaster-prepared.

Given the significant relationship between physical activity engagement and disaster preparedness among college students, it is recommended that universities incorporate physical fitness programs into their disaster preparedness initiatives. This could include courses or workshops emphasizing physical fitness and emergency preparedness skills, such as CPR training, first aid, and emergency response exercises. Additionally, promoting a physically active lifestyle through campus-wide campaigns and providing accessible fitness facilities can enhance students' resilience and readiness for unexpected events. Integrating these elements into university policies could foster a more prepared and resilient student community. Lastly, the researchers recommended future researchers as a reference point, expanding upon its findings through additional studies or exploring different aspects of physical activity engagement and disaster preparedness among college students.

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